

CAPPARIS SPINOSA L. PLANTS PHARMACEUTICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

In this article Frankincense (P. harmala), Kovul, Kovar (Capparis spinosa L.) plants' biological and medicinal properties are described.

Key words: *Isiriq (P. harmala), Kovul, Kovar (Capparis spinosa L.), Nurota mountains and Koytash, Baliglitov, Pistalitog, Yetimtog ridges, handonpista, walnut, almond, namatak, cumin, zirk.*

Capparis spinosa (Capparis spinosa L.) is a semi-shrub belonging to the Capparis family. The stem and branches are horizontal, the leaf is oval, the flower is large, white or light pink. The fruit is red fleshy and has many seeds. Kovul or kavar plant is a natural medicinal plant that can be found in our republic in Zomin, Gallaorol, Forish, Sharaf Rashidov districts of Jizzakh region. The buds and fruits of the kovull are eaten with vinegar or salt. The fruit contains 18% protein and 36% oil. It is a multi-seeded berry that grows in deserts and hills, on roadsides, on walls, among crops, and its fruits are fleshy, up to 2 cm long. Seeds ripen in July-August. The fruits of this medicinal plant contain saponins, alkaloids, 32.9 percent carbohydrates, 150 mg ascorbic acid, 3.75 percent oil, stachydrin alkaloid in the root bark.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 5032 dated May 3, 2017, "Nukus-farm", "Zomin-farm", "Kosonsoy-farm", "Sirdaryo-farm" in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Jizzakh, Namangan, Syrdaryo, Surkhondarya and Tashkent regions, "Boysun-farm", "Bostonliq-farm" and "Parkent-farm" free economic zones were established.

It grows naturally on the mountain slopes of our country. This thorn bush, which grows freely in the ground, does not choose a place, it is resistant to dehydration and cold. It grows from May to October. The plant is used not only in the preparation of medicine, this plant is also used as an aromatic and useful spice in many countries.

Koval is healing from root to leaf. Therefore, it is highly valued as a valuable raw material in the pharmaceutical industry. The fruit contains saponins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, ascorbic acid, oil, stachydrin alkaloid in the root bark. The root, dug up in early spring, is dried and made into a medicine for allergy sufferers. Even before the flowering season, a decoction is made that cures allergies. It is noted that the tincture obtained from the root part of the plant is a cure for hepatitis, the stem and leaves are useful for skin diseases, and the iodine contained in the fruit is beneficial for people suffering from measles. Preparation of drugs based on these recommendations is widely implemented in the world pharmaceutical industry.

In addition to being a medicinal plant, cranberry is also used in food. Buds, buds, and developing fruits of saffron are marinated in acetic acid and used in food as a medicine known as capers. Hindus call the snake by the names of cobra, kabra or kabarra, and they like to eat food prepared with the addition of plant organs.

Ripe fruit, leaves, stem and root bark are used in medicine. Unopened buds and leaves are picked in May-August. At the same time, the bark of young, woody branches and roots is removed, crushed and dried in the sun or at a temperature of 50-60°C. A decoction made from the bark has an appetizing effect. It is used in folk medicine to treat purulent wounds. Pressing freshly squeezed bark on an aching tooth gives a positive result. Sometimes it has an antiseptic effect when applied to open purulent wounds. In addition, the plant is used in the treatment of angina pectoris, thyrotoxicosis, hemorrhoids, and diabetes.

To make nastoika from root bark, 0.5 liters of boiled water is poured over 20 g of crushed bark, and it is left to stand for 1-2 hours. Drink 1/2 cup three times a day before meals. It's no secret that the once neglected and growing in the hills and deserts, the saffron is medicinal from root to leaf and is in high demand.

Figure 1. *Capparis spinosa* L.

(saponins (lat. Saponis-soap) are nitrogen-free complex organic compounds belonging to the group of glucosides. Saponin has a bitter taste, a sharp smell, foams like soap when shaken. Pure saponin is a colorless or yellowish amorphous substance. When dissolved in water, colloidal solutions are formed. Aqueous solutions are oils and Barcapop with resins gives emulsions. As a result of acid or enzymatic hydrolysis, saponin breaks down into monosaccharides and the non-carbohydrate part - aglycone (sapogenin).

BOOKS

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